

VITAMIN C AND TOXINS. PART III. THE EFFECT OF DIPHTHERIA TOXIN ON VITAMIN C METABOLISM.

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A decrease in the ascorbic acid content of the blood, adrenal, liver and kidney of guinea-pigs was observed after the injection of 0.5 m.l.d. of diphtheria toxin. During the period of intoxication a greater amount of ascorbic acid has been found to be excreted in the urine in a combined state.

We have previously observed that vitamin C *in vitro* has some specific inactivating effect on diphtheria toxin but that ingestion of massive doses of vitamin C can hardly confer any protection on experimental guinea-pigs when injected subsequently with 1 m.l.d. of diphtheria toxin (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **15**, 438, 443). Zilva (*Brit. J. Expt. Path.*, 1937, **18**, 449) also found that guinea-pigs, when grouped as depleted, saturated or injected with ascorbic acid, behave practically identically to 1 m.l.d. of diphtheria toxin. King and Menten (*J. Nutrition*, 1935, **10**, 129, 141), however, have shown that when animals are partially depleted of their vitamin C reserves, their survival period after injection of diphtheria toxin is shortened about 50% and the loss in body-weight is more severe. Moreover, it was observed by various investigators (Lyman and King, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1936, **56**, 209; Philippe and Harde, *Compt. rend. soc. biol.*, 1936, **121**, 940; Torrance, *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.*, 1937, **35**, 654; Polonyi, *Wied. Med. Wochsch.*, 1935, **85**, 685; Haas, *Z. Immunitätsforsch.*, 1937, **91**, 203; Harris, Passmore and Pagel, *Lancet*, 1937, **233**, 183) that injection of diphtheria toxin in sublethal doses causes a depletion of vitamin C content of tissues of normally fed guinea-pigs. The diminution of the ascorbic acid in the adrenal or in other organs of guinea-pigs, indicates that during intoxication vitamin C metabolism is affected. Harris *et al.* (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1936, **55**, 841) and others (Rinehart *et al.*, *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.*, 1936, **35**, 347, 350) have observed that during fever and other conditions like rheumatism and tuberculosis, the vitamin C excretion in the urine is appreciably lowered and larger amounts of vitamin C require to be administered in order to maintain normal excretory level of vitamin C in the urine. Since the recent observations of Scarborough and Stewart (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, **31**, 2232) and the observations of Guha and Sen-Gupta (*Nature*, 1938, **141**, 974) indicate that in normal urine a certain amount of ascorbic acid is

excreted in a combined form, it was considered of interest to investigate whether during toxic condition a greater amount of ascorbic acid is excreted in the combined state, thereby reducing the amount of free ascorbic acid excreted. Thus ascorbic acid might serve as an internal detoxicating agent both in natural and infected conditions. A detailed investigation of the effect of diphtheria toxin (taken as an infective agent) on the ascorbic acid concentration of blood, tissues and urine of guinea-pigs was therefore, carried out in order to throw light on the fate of ascorbic acid during the period of intoxication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Guinea-pigs were kept on a normal mixed diet of green grass and germinated gram. The animals, weighing between 280-350 g. were divided into several groups, each containing 5 animals. One group served as control while the other 4 groups were injected with 0.5 m.l.d. of standardised diphtheria toxin. Blood was drawn out from the heart of the guinea-pigs of these 4 groups 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours after toxin injection respectively, while the animals of the control group supplied figures for normal blood ascorbic acid. The ascorbic acid content was determined from 2 c.c. of oxalated blood by the usual titrimetric method (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 30) after precipitation of protein by trichloroacetic acid. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

No. of expt.	Normal.	Mg. of ascorbic acid per 100 c.c. of blood.			
		Hours after 0.5 m.l.d. of diphtheria toxin injection.			
		24.	48.	72.	96.
1	0.64	0.65	0.47	0.30	0.50
2	0.65	0.74	0.54	0.43	0.37
3	0.76	0.43	0.47	0.40	0.52
4	0.65	0.40	0.50	0.40	0.44
5	0.65	0.40	0.55	0.43	0.35
Mean	0.67	0.52	0.50	0.39	0.43

It will be seen that there is a progressive decrease in the ascorbic acid value of the blood of guinea-pigs but there is a slight increase 3 days after toxin injection.

Similar experiments were carried out with other groups of guinea-pigs in order to estimate the vitamin C content of the adrenal, liver and kidney 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours after the injection of 0.5 m.l.d. of toxin (Table II). There is, it will be seen, about 50% decrease in the ascorbic acid content of the adrenal as compared with that of normals and there is also a definite reduction of the ascorbic acid content of the liver and kidney tissues after toxin injection.

TABLE II.

A. *Adrenal.*

Mg. of ascorbic acid per g. of adrenal.

No. of expt.	Normal.	Hours after 0.5 m.l.d. of diphtheria toxin injection			
		24.	48.	72.	96.
1	0.348	0.220	0.216	0.172	0.180
2	0.366	0.277	0.200	0.170	0.200
3	0.366	0.290	0.360	0.195	0.215
4	0.330	0.300	0.277	0.225	0.161
5	0.290	0.305	0.340	0.205	0.191
Mean	0.340	0.278	0.278	0.193	0.189

B. *Liver.*

Mg. of ascorbic acid per 5 g. of liver.

No. of expt.	Normal.	Hours after 0.5 m.l.d. of diphtheria toxin injection.			
		24.	48.	72.	96.
1	1.04	0.98	1.23	1.00	0.81
2	1.50	1.13	1.00	0.96	1.13
3	1.50	1.04	1.15	1.04	1.00
4	1.36	1.28	1.13	1.15	0.87
5	0.92	1.50	1.15	1.15	1.04
Mean	1.26	1.18	1.13	1.06	0.97

TABLE II (contd.).

C. *Kidney.*

Mg. of ascorbic acid per g. of kidney.

No. of expt.	Normal.	Hours after 0.5 m.l.d. of diphtheria toxin injection.			
		24.	48.	72.	96.
1	0.136	0.105	0.132	0.103	0.097
2	0.139	0.113	0.098	0.109	0.123
3	0.161	0.138	0.143	0.100	0.103
4	0.151	0.134	0.132	0.120	0.100
5	0.100	0.134	0.112	0.114	0.110
Mean	0.137	0.124	0.123	0.109	0.106

The estimation of ascorbic acid content (both free and combined) of the urine of guinea-pigs was carried out by the following method. Each animal was kept in a metabolism cage. The urine was collected over sufficient quantity of glacial acetic acid so that the final concentration of ascorbic acid remained near about 10% after washing the cage and funnel. Thiosulphate excreted in the urine was removed by addition of barium acetate (2 g.). This was centrifuged. From the supernatant liquid excess of barium was removed by addition of dilute sulphuric acid. This was centrifuged and was made up to a definite volume (50 c.c.) and stored in an amber coloured bottle. Into this urine H_2S was passed for 5 minutes and the bottle then well-corked. After $\frac{1}{2}$ hour an aliquot was taken out, H_2S was removed by a current of inert gas (CO_2 or N_2) and the vitamin C content was estimated by the usual method. A portion (5 c.c.) of this H_2S -free urine was brought to p_H 5.6, to which 2 c.c. of acetate buffer (p_H 5.6) and 1 c.c. of ascorbic acid oxidase solution (prepared freshly from pressed cucumber juice) were added. The mixture was well shaken and kept at 40° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The contents were made up to a definite volume (10 c.c.) and the reducing substances present were estimated. The difference between the values obtained before and after oxidase treatment gives the true ascorbic acid value (*cf.* Sen-Gupta and Guha, *Science and Culture*, 1938, 8, 398). The remaining urine solution was kept in H_2S atmosphere for a period of 72 hours after which an aliquot was taken out and similarly its true vitamin C content was estimated. After 96 hours of reduction in H_2S atmosphere the remaining portion of the urine was likewise treated. The maximum value of true ascorbic acid is obtained between 72 and 96 hours of reduction in H_2S atmosphere. For present purpose the difference

between the initial value and the maximum value obtained after H_2S treatment has been taken to be the amount of ascorbic acid present in combined state (*cf.* Scarborough and Stewart, *loc. cit.*). *

In the present set of experiments each guinea-pig was employed as a self-controlled animal. The urine was estimated for 2 or 3 days before and after 0.5 m. l. d. of diphtheria toxin injection. The results (Table III) show that in almost all cases there is a decrease in free ascorbic acid excretion and an increase in the combined ascorbic acid (released after H_2S -treatment) after intoxication. There is, of course, no quantitative correlation between the diminution of urinary ascorbic acid and increase in ascorbigen following intoxication, as even under normal circumstances the urinary excretion of ascorbic acid and ascorbigen vary considerably from day to day. Also the extra ascorbigen in urine in some cases may account for some of the loss of ascorbic acid from the tissues.

TABLE III.

Mg. of ascorbic acid excreted in the urine during 24 hours per guinea-pig.

No. of expt.	No. of days.	Free ascorbic acid.		Combined ascorbic acid in terms of ascorbic acid.	
		Before toxin injection.	After toxin injection.	Before toxin injection.	After toxin injection.
I.	1	0.387	0.299	0.279	0.317
	2	0.398	0.277	0.215	0.253
	3	0.337	0.148	0.313	0.371
	Mean	0.374	0.241	0.269	0.313
II.	1	0.330	0.256	0.231	0.463
	2	0.271	0.270	0.241	0.452
	3	0.261	0.192	0.224	0.248
	Mean	0.287	0.239	0.232	0.387
III.	1	0.387	0.291	0.275	0.449
	2	0.330	0.286	0.324	0.461
	3	0.257	0.292	0.443	0.362
	Mean	0.324	0.289	0.347	0.424

* This question, however, has not yet been settled and further work is in progress.

TABLE III (contd.).

IV.	1	0.300	0.360	0.337	0.256
	2	0.377	0.249	0.313	0.429
	Mean	0.338	0.304	0.325	0.342
V.	1	0.310	0.310	0.325	0.365
	2	0.415	0.360	0.337	0.498
	Mean	0.362	0.335	0.331	0.431
VI.	1	0.375	0.233	0.345	0.417
	2	0.325	0.200	0.202	0.415
	Mean	0.350	0.216	0.273	0.416
VII.	1	0.520	0.375	0.170	0.425
	2	0.390	0.357	0.107	0.391
	Mean	0.455	0.366	0.138	0.408

C O N C L U S I O N .

A decrease in the ascorbic acid content of the blood of normally fed guinea-pigs was observed on the 2nd, 3rd and 4th days after the injection of 0.5 m. l. d. of diphtheria toxin.

Similar injection of 0.5 m. l. d. of diphtheria toxin causes a diminution of the ascorbic acid content of adrenal, liver and kidney of guinea pigs. The loss in the adrenal gland is about 50%.

During the period of intoxication a greater amount of ascorbic acid is excreted in the urine in a combined state and a smaller amount in the free state. The combined ascorbic acid excreted may account for the loss of free ascorbic acid in the urine and also for the loss in the tissues during infection.

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